

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF BLADDER DETRUSOR WEIGHT IN BENIGN PROSTATIC HYPERPLASIA DIAGNOSIS.

Saidakhror Kariev ¹
Otabek Khudoyberdiev ²
Saidaziz Kariev ²

¹ Department of Urology and Andrology, Center for the Development of Professional Qualification of Medical Workers.

² 1st City Clinic Hospital named after Ibn Sina, Tashkent.
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Introduction:

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a frequent urological disorder associated with obstructive and irritative lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS). Using the International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS), these symptoms are graded for severity (mild, moderate, or severe). Bladder wall thickness and detrusor muscle weight increase as physiological and pathological changes associated with BPH.

Keywords:

BPH, IPSS, bladder detrusor weight, LUTS.

Objective:

To determine the correlation between bladder detrusor weight and IPSS questionnaire scores.

Materials and Methods:

126 patients diagnosed with BPH and who also completed the IPSS questionnaire were included in the study. Ultrasound was used to measure bladder wall thickness in all patients. The weight of the bladder detrusor was calculated as the volume of the bladder minus the intravesical volume multiplied by the density of detrusor muscle ($\rho = 1.04 \text{ g/cm}^3$). The outcomes of IPSS were analyzed concerning the obstructive, irritative, and total symptom scores.

Results:

Patients had an average age of 67.3 ± 8.2 years. The mean total IPSS score was 16.5 ± 6.8 , of which obstructive and irritative symptom scores were 9.2 ± 4.1 and 7.3 ± 3.5 , respectively. Mean bladder detrusor weight was 35.7 ± 15.4 grams.

Positive correlation analysis showed that bladder detrusor weight was significantly correlated with total International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS) score ($r = 0.62$), obstructive ($r = 0.68$), and irritative symptom scores ($r = 0.55$, $p < 0.001$). These results suggest that increased bladder detrusor weight correlates positively with severity of BPH symptoms.

Conclusion:

Bladder detrusor weight is positively correlated with severity of LUTS in BPH patients. Detrusor weight data can help assess progression of disease and optimize treatment strategies in BPH.

